

A CYBER-PHYSICAL SYSTEM FOR INVENTORY MANAGEMENT: INTEGRATING COMPUTER VISION WITH DOBOT ROBOTIC ARM

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Abstract

This paper presents a cyber-physical pick-and-place laboratory that integrates the Dobot Magician, computer vision, and inventory databases as an educational innovation to cultivate Industry 5.0 competencies at the University degree level during an Erasmus+ research internship. Within the CODEMO project-supported learning environment, students engage in active, project-based methodologies to design, implement, and monitor autonomous stock management solutions, fostering human–robot collaboration, data-driven decision-making, and technological readiness.

Robotic manipulators are often used in industry to improve efficiency and precision, particularly in repetitive tasks. This project presents a laboratory-scale pick-and-place system that uses the Dobot Magician robotic arm to automate inventory management. It implements real-time object detection combined with robotic automation. This system can recognise and identify items detected by a webcam using the YOLO model. After that, the Dobot robot categorises items into different spots for better inventory management. The system features a user-friendly monitoring and manual operation interface, along with a log to track facility movements. Additionally, it is connected to a database that stores all movement logs and product information, ensuring data persistence and allowing the retrieval of historical records, as well as the monitoring of inventory levels. It was found that the system can automate inventory management with minimal human intervention and reduce errors. This paper presents an application-oriented approach for engineering university students to gain knowledge on Industry 5.0 concepts.

Keywords: Robotic Automation, Object Detection, educational, innovation, active methodologies, Erasmus+, Industry 5.0.

1 INTRODUCTION

With automation and robotics revolutionizing the industries to operate more efficiently and accurately, the world has been changing rapidly. In response to the need for smarter and more efficient industrial machines, there has been a large amount of research into the area of robotics [1], [2], [3]. Specifically, the aim is to increase the intelligence of robots while also improving their capabilities. Among these products to come to market is the Dobot robotic arm, which is a multi-purpose and versatile device that can perform simple pick-and-place operations as well as complex assembly operations.

Parallel to these technological advances, higher education institutions are increasingly required to adapt their teaching methodologies to better prepare students for rapidly evolving industrial environments. Active learning approaches, such as project-based learning, problem-based learning, and experiential learning, have proven effective in developing technical skills, critical thinking, and autonomy by engaging students directly in realistic engineering challenges [4]. In this context, laboratory-based learning environments that integrate robotics, computer vision, and data management systems provide an ideal framework for fostering hands-on experience and Industry 5.0-related competences.

Developments in the automation world offer the continued evolution of robotic arms added with computer vision systems [5]. This paper discusses a few of these advancements along with few areas of development in each discipline Robotics and Computer Vision. The YOLO (You Only Look Once) model was proposed by Redmon and Farhadi (2019), allowing real time object detection with high speed and high accuracy [6]. The YOLO model fits best with robotic applications that process real time data providing updates for tasks such as object identification and tracking. Nugroho et al. (2023) integrated robotic arms and computer vision systems for automated pick and place operations [7]. Details on the issues of coordinates, feedback control loops between the arm and the vision systems are explained along with solutions stated by the experts. Experts addressed the use of robust robotic system simulations to take

the pressure from relying on real hardware systems and increase the speed of development. Although they provide a lot of possibilities, the integration of robotic arms and computer vision still faces a lot of problems. First, is the coordination between robot arms and perception system, second, is occlusions, third is changing lighting conditions, and last the reliability and robustness of the systems.

This paper presents the functioning of a Dobot and its possible integration with a computer vision system such as YOLO, so that the robot can detect objects. With this combination the robotic arm can now "see" and identify objects, allowing for the automation of an operation requiring both identification and operation. As a result, not only is productivity enhanced, but human intervention is reduced in the process, improving efficiency and consistency. This article will fully explore the technical aspects of the Dobot robotic arm, how it moves, and the function of databases in tracking operations of the Dobot robotic arm. In this paper the gaps in these areas are investigated, and the following questions (Q) are covered.

- Q1. How Dobot robotic arm can be integrated with YOLO object detection model to design an automated pick-and-place system?
- Q2. What are the challenges regarding achieving coordination between the robotic arm and the vision system in real time, and how can they be met?

By answering these questions, the university students can engage in developing more efficient, advanced systems in the field of automation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, products were manipulated with a Dobot Magician robotic arm with a suction cup. A camera was attached to the YOLO model for object detection. The entire configuration was implemented in Python, using libraries such as OpenCV for computer vision, Tkinter for the graphical interface, PyDobot for robotic control, Flask for web integration, and additional modules including NumPy, PIL, and JSON for data handling, and was configured to evaluate the performance of the system for detecting and/or manipulating objects in an automated stream. A schematic overview of the full pipeline is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Vision-guided robotic pick-and-place pipeline.

2.1 Computer Vision

In this study, a camera was used as the primary vision sensor because it generates a high-quality video stream (necessary for real time object detection using the YOLO model). Fig. 2 shows the flexible adjustment stand used to mount the Logitech HD Pro C920 camera, increasing precision for the optimum position above the workspace for object detection. The camera has automatic focus and low-light enhancement capabilities, meaning it can perform in any lighting of either a laboratory or industrial setting as lighting can present poor distinguishing contrast. The camera connects via USB allowing a direct connection to the Python control system for real-time data streaming capabilities between the camera and YOLO detection module.

Figure 2. Logitech HD Pro C920 camera mounted above the workspace

Figure 3. Mechanical structure of Dobot Magician.

2.2 Dobot Magician

The Dobot Magician is a multifunctional desktop robotic arm designed for education, research, and light industrial applications, capable of performing tasks such as pick-and-place, 3D printing, laser engraving, and writing/drawing, with support for programming, computer vision, and automation integration.

2.2.1 Arm Structure

The Dobot Magician is a robotic arm that has four degrees of freedom (DOF). The robotic arm consists of a base, shoulder, elbow, and wrist [8]. The base, shoulder, and elbow use stepper motors, and the wrist uses a servo motor. The Dobot Magician's end-effector accepts several attachments: suction cups, grippers, laser printer, 3D printing hot-end, and a pen holder for drawing graphs.

The Dobot Magician has a structure diagram with four joints (J1, J2, J3, and J4). Position J2 is the initial position for center of balance at (0, 0, 0) and when the robotic arm is in motion, it is going to position it as (x, y, z). The Dobot Magician has an active power supply and has active light indicators. The manipulator for the Dobot Magician has a forearm length of 135 mm from its base, a rear arm length of 147 mm, a front arm length of 160 mm, and a length of 72 mm for the end effector. Fig. 3 shows the mechanical structure diagram for the Dobot Magician. The robot's working area is described as having a maximum reach of 320 mm. The base (Joint 1) rotates within a range of -135° to $+135^\circ$, while the rear arm (Joint 2) moves from 0° to $+85^\circ$. The forearm (Joint 3) has a motion range of -10° to $+95^\circ$, and the wrist (Joint 4) rotates between -90° and $+90^\circ$.

2.2.2 Suction Cup End-Effector

For product handling, the robot arm is equipped with a pneumatic suction cup to function as the end-effector in product handling. The end-effector can securely grip objects with flat or slight curvature, minimizing the risk of both slipping or product damage.

The programming of robotic control and coordination was performed in Python using both the Dobot SDK, used for key low-level programming such as calibration and homing, ensuring the arm could start from a consistent reference position and the open-source PyDobot library, used to interface with the robot in real-time including point-to-point commands, and end-effector control. The vision system

consisted of the YOLOv8 object detection model which enabled the robot to detect products and provide real-time information on a product's location and classification.

Once all of the robotic components are integrated to function in a single workspace using the vision system, Dobot Magician robotic arm, and pneumatic suction cup end-effector, A completely integrated workspace has been designed for efficient automated pick-and-place operations (Fig. 4).

3 RESULTS

One of the greatest accomplishments of this work is the confidence and high accuracy of the vision-guided robotic system. The YOLOv8 model, trained on a custom dataset of 16 consumer products, achieved an average detection accuracy of 95% while working even under uncontrolled lighting condition (Fig. 5).

This detection accuracy was maintained across product appearances regardless of the variations in colour, shape of the packaging, and orientation. After several tests, the confidence threshold was found to be 0.7 (70%) to allow for a balance between finding each product and having the fewest false positives. After detecting the product, the vision-guided robotic control system activates the Dobot arm to complete the designated sequence: it moves the arm to the designated pickup zone, turns on the suction cup, moves it to the existing waypoint coordinates, and finally deposits the applicable object in the correct storage location when the arm is in position. The robotic arm demonstrated a high level of repeatability, positional errors were only at most ± 1 mm, which confirms the robotic arm's high accuracy for online manipulation tasks. This demonstrates the robustness of the end-to-end pipeline and the integration of computer vision for real-time robotic manipulation.

Figure 4. Logitech HD Pro C920 camera mounted above the workspace.

Figure 5. Real-Time Object Detection Output.

Correct robotic operation is always dependent on proper calibration, which was crucial when trying to achieve a reliable and high performing system. Upon startup, the Dobot Magician does a homing routine, where each joint for its seventeen degrees of freedom, moves to its physical limit defined by Hall effect sensors to reset the coordinate and provide a reference frame. This ensures all subsequent PTP (Point-to-Point commands) can be achieved from a given known origin with drift or cumulative positioning being removed.

3.1 Data Management and Remote Monitoring

This system includes a data-management digital layer that creates additional transparency, traceability, and relationship between end-users and the system (as shown in Fig. 6). The graphical user interface (GUI) is designed to provide real-time interaction and monitoring of the intelligent detection and manipulation process.

The GUI displays a live video feed where users can visualize the detection zones and the objects identified by the YOLO model. Each detection zone can be dynamically created, resized, or deleted, allowing users to customize the system according to their needs. The selected zone is highlighted, ensuring clarity on which area is currently active. Every successful manipulation, whether it is an Automatic-Deposit or a Manual-Picking, is recorded in a JSON-based database. This database logs essential details such as:

- Timestamp: The exact date and time of the action.

- Product: The name of the product involved.
- Storage Position: The location where the product is stored or retrieved.
- Action Type: The nature of the action (e.g., "Automatic-Deposit", "Manual-Picking").

This traceability ensures that all operations are documented, providing a complete audit trail for each product's lifecycle within the system.

The data-management layer is the backbone of the system, ensuring that every action is accurately recorded and easily accessible. This layer not only maintains the integrity of the data but also enhances the system's usability.

The integration of a Flask-based web dashboard into the intelligent detection system introduces a significant advancement in remote monitoring and inventory management. As illustrated in Fig. 6, this dashboard provides users with real-time access to the system's inventory status, including the quantity and storage position of each product. By simply opening a web browser, users can remotely monitor the live condition of the inventory, facilitating efficient decision-making and proactive management. The dashboard displays a comprehensive overview of the stock status, with each product listed alongside its corresponding position and quantity. This real-time visibility allows users to quickly identify stock levels, detect shortages, and make informed decisions to optimize inventory management.

The dashboard displays a comprehensive overview of the stock status, with each product listed alongside its corresponding position and quantity. This real-time visibility allows users to quickly identify stock levels, detect shortages, and make informed decisions to optimize inventory management. One of the key features of the dashboard is its reset capability, which allows users to reinitialize the inventory status when necessary. This functionality is particularly valuable in scenarios requiring system maintenance or the start of a new operational cycle, ensuring that the system remains accurate and up to date.

This web-based interface embodies the principles of Industry 4.0, where cyber-physical systems merge physical processes with digital interfaces to create smarter and more efficient operations. By enabling remote supervision and control, the dashboard enhances the system's responsiveness and operational efficiency, aligning with the broader goals of Industry 4.0 to create interconnected and intelligent manufacturing environments. The ability to monitor and manage inventory remotely not only improves convenience but also supports swift and informed decision-making, ultimately contributing to more streamlined and effective operations.

Figure 6. Graphical user interface.

Figure 7. Real-time stock status dashboard of the Intelligent Detection System.

Additionally, to avoid unsuccessful operations, the platform incorporates a real-time stock validation feature, which will automatically check the availability of a product prior to performing a picking task. If the missing item is not found in the stock database, the user interface will create an alert window shortly

thereafter stating product name and missing item from stock, as depicted in Fig. 8. The validation feature avoids unnecessary robot movements and ensures effective operations while also giving the user immediate response to update stock or choose an alternative product.

Figure 8. Out-of-stock alert during picking operation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated the successful design and implementation of an operational cyber-physical inventory management system that combines computer vision, robotic manipulation, real-time data logging, and database integration. Leveraging low-cost hardware and open-source software, the proposed solution effectively automated product identification, classification, and storage with minimal human intervention. The integration of a Dobot Magician robotic arm with a vision-based detection model proved to be well-suited for laboratory-scale and small, structured environments, offering reliable handling of heterogeneous products while maintaining accuracy and repeatability.

Beyond its technical performance, the system serves as a valuable, application-oriented learning platform, enabling users to engage with core concepts related to intelligent automation, human–robot collaboration, and data-driven inventory control. The inclusion of monitoring interfaces, manual override capabilities, and persistent data storage enhances transparency, traceability, and operational understanding, which are critical aspects of modern industrial systems.

Hence, this work has both theoretical and practical implications for the small-scale cyber-physical automation area. At the theoretical level, it can be noticed that: (i) it supports the work of [5, 6] by demonstrating how discrete technologies can be incorporated in intelligent systems, and (ii) it extends the literature on Industry 5.0 by providing a human-centric approach on inventory management and emphasizing the importance of human-robot collaboration. At the practical level, it brings forward a fully operational tool that supports traceability and data-driven control in both educational and organizational environments.

Future developments may focus on extending the physical infrastructure by incorporating conveyor belts or additional handling mechanisms to enable continuous material flow and higher throughput. From a digital perspective, scalability and decision-making capabilities could be strengthened by integrating cloud-based services, enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems, and advanced analytics to support predictive and autonomous inventory management. Expanding connectivity and system intelligence would facilitate experimentation with more complex warehouse scenarios and adaptive control strategies.

Overall, by tightly coupling physical automation with digital technologies, this project aligns with contemporary Industry 4.0 and emerging Industry 5.0 principles, where interconnected, intelligent systems enhance efficiency while supporting human-centric operation. The presented approach offers a scalable foundation for both educational and applied research contexts, contributing to the development of flexible, responsive, and technologically advanced inventory management solutions.

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